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Tahririyat manzili: 150107

Farg'ona shahri, Farg'ona ko'chasi, 86 - uy

Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

@Alferganus_ltd

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Адрес редакции: 150107

г. Фергана, ул. Ферганская, 86

Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

@Alferganus_ltd

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Nishonov Farkhod Musajonovich
*Academic Lyceum of Fergana
Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan*

Urmonov Alisherjon Adhamovich
*Head of Department, Fergana Regional
Branch of Hamkorbank Joint-Stock
Commercial Bank with participation of
foreign capital, Uzbekistan*

ISSUES OF TECHNOLOGICAL AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRY

Abstract: Aspects of the current stage of development of innovations in the world are considered. The directions of development of the innovation sphere in the world until 2030 are analyzed. On the basis of the analysis, the most promising directions for the development of innovative activity in Uzbekistan are identified, which will contribute to the country's transition to a new technological order in the future.

Key words: innovation, innovation process, innovation system, technology, economic growth.

Нишонов Фарход Мусажонович
Академический лицей Ферганского политехнического института, Узбекистан

Урмонов Алишержон Адхамович
*Начальник отдела, Ферганский региональный филиал Акционерно-
коммерческий банк Hamkorbank с участием иностранного капитала,
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**ВОПРОСЫ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО И ИННОВАЦИОННОГО
РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ**

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены аспекты современного этапа развития инноваций в мире. Проанализированы направления развития инновационной сферы в мире до 2030 года. На основе проведенного анализа выделяются наиболее перспективные направления развития инновационной деятельности в Узбекистане, что будет способствовать переходу страны в будущем на новый технологический уклад.

Ключевые слова: инновация, инновационный процесс, инновационная система, технологии, экономический рост.

**СANOАТНИ ТЕХНОЛОГИК ВА ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ
МАСАЛАЛАРИ****Нишонов Фарход Мусажонович***Фаргона политехника институти академик лицейи, Ўзбекистон***Ўрмонов Алишержон Адхамович***Ҳамкорбанк хорижий капитал иштирокидаги акциядорлик-тижорат
банки Фаргона минтақа филиали бўлим бошлиғи*

Аннотация: Мақолада дунёда инновацион ривожланишининг ҳозирги босқичи айрим жиҳатлари кўриб чиқилган бўлиб, жумладан жаҳонда 2030 йилгача инновация соҳасини ривожлантириши йўналишлари таҳлил қилинган. Таҳлиллар асосида Ўзбекистонда инновацияларни ривожлантиришининг энг истиқболли йўналишлари аниқланиб, улар келажакда мамлакатнинг янги технологик тартибга ўтишини кўрсатиб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: инновация, инновацион жараён, инновацион тизим, технологиялар, иқтисодий ўсиш.

At the present stage of development, the world economy is on the 5th technological order that builds on the achievements in the field of microelectronics, computer science, biotechnology, genetic engineering, new forms of energy, materials, space exploration, satellite communications, etc. There is a transition from isolated firms to a single network of large and small companies connected electronic network based on the Internet, been working in close cooperation in the field of technology, quality control, planning innovation [1]. Currently, according to the prevailing rate of long-term technical and economic development, the technological order is close to the limits of its growth - splash and drop in energy prices, the global financial crisis - a sure sign of the final phase of the life cycle of the dominant technological order and the beginning of economic restructuring on based on the following order. Is being formed today reproductive system of the new, the sixth technological order, the

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emergence and growth of which will determine the global economic development in the next two to three decades [2]. Its contours are only beginning to emerge in the developed world, primarily in the US, Japan and China, and are characterized by targeting the development and application of high technologies ("high-tech"). Sixth technological order will be characterized by the development of robotics technologies based on advances in molecular biology and genetic engineering, nanotechnology, artificial intelligence systems, global information networks, high-speed integrated transport systems — synthesis of the achievements in these areas should lead to, for example, a quantum computer, artificial intelligence, and ultimately provide access to a new level in the systems of government, society, economy. On this basis the main directions of development of innovations for the period up to 2030 will be the world's next priorities [3]:

- Further application of new developments in information and communication technologies in the extractive industries, manufacturing and services;
- Continue to develop new materials for the manufacture of advanced technologies in many industries: electronics, aerospace, automotive, construction industry, etc.;
- Beginning of a breakthrough in the sectors related to human health - biotechnology, diagnostics, treatments, new medicines, patient care, etc.;
- The emergence of entirely new technologies to improve the quality of life, based on the association of nanotechnology, biotechnology, information technology and cognitive science; will be technically possible to significantly expand the biological potential of human, etc.

Period of replacement of technological orders in the leading countries burdened by overcapacity outdated technological order creates for lagging countries a window of opportunity for a technological breakthrough. It thus occurred "economic miracles" of the past century. In recent years, the practice of leading developed and developing countries, there is a shift in focus formation of topics of science and technology towards the search for answers to the so-called Grand Challenges, with which the economy and society will face in the medium and long term.

Among the "base set" of global challenges, formed on the basis of key overseas, the following stand out challenges and trends of the global scale:

- exhaustion of stocks of strategic mineral resources, the search for new sources of energy and energy security;
- an aging population, changing lifestyles of man and society, the growth of socially significant diseases, including cancer and cardiovascular;
- greening the economy and "green growth" associated with the transition to the "carbon" society;
- development of new models of economic development, including the

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transformation of global value chains;

- transition of the global economy to a new stage of technological development, accompanied by a radical change in the sectorial structure and sources (factors) of competitiveness;
- strengthens the role of inter-branch technologies and interdisciplinary studies, including socio-economic and humanitarian.

In the current context of the global of development high-quality sustainable economic growth is possible only on the basis of the concentration of resources on the formation of a new cutting-edge areas of the 6th technological order requiring multiple increase innovation and investment activities. For a country whose economy has a sufficiently diversified industrial structure, the choice of strategy cannot be universal for all industries and sectors. For Uzbekistan, in modern conditions, the optimum direction of the formation and development of NIS should be mixed strategy of innovative development with elements of "borrowing and adaptation of foreign technology and to enhance their own innovative potential".

The most important areas of the emergence and spread of new technologies and the development of innovative activity in the real sector of the economy of Uzbekistan for the period up to 2030 should be allocated:

- the development of modern electronics, microelectronics, photonics and electronic instrument;
- creation of modern laser, electron nuclear, ion, plasma, ion-photon processing technologies and new materials;
- creation of high-technology machinery and equipment, instruments, reference tools, methods of measurement and control systems for economic sectors;
- development of biotechnologies based on the achievements of modern genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and bioinformatics, chemical engineering and nanotechnology;
- design and development of new high-performance technologies and devices that use renewable energy (solar energy, hydropower, wind power, bio-energy);
- preparation of nanostructured materials of different functionality from the natural and manmade materials;
- development of high-performance technologies of production of new drugs based on natural (plants, animals, microorganisms, etc.) and synthetic raw materials;
- creation of energy- and resource-saving and environmentally friendly new materials with using nanotechnology;
- and other.

When selecting priorities in the fields of economy of Uzbekistan emphasis should be placed precisely on the trends and technologies that will give the maximum

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effect of increasing the competitiveness of production and social development. Obvious and fundamental points of growth at different stages of NIS should be: firstly, the construction machinery industry, producing innovative equipment, secondly, a high-tech engineering industry that update the equipment at the present level of quality and, thirdly, a special role in this list in a time of global informatization of the world economy must borrow information, communication and connectivity. Thus, there are next industries:

- sub-sectors of mechanical engineering and metalworking (instrumentation, electronics, radio industries, communications, repair of machinery and equipment);
- sub-sectors of medical industry (manufacturing of medical equipment, manufacture of medical devices made of glass, porcelain and plastic, chemical and pharmaceutical industry);
- sub-sector of chemical and petrochemical industry (industry of chemical fibers and threads, etc.).

In this connection the priority areas for the implementation of advanced technologies in the fields of economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan may become:

- Energy, energy- and resource saving. Development and implementation of new energy saving technologies, autonomous sources of heat and electricity, search renewable alternative energy sources (solar and wind, bioenergy). For example: the development and implementation of effective biogas plants for the production of combustible gas and fertilizer from animal waste, crop, specially grown biomass.
- Informatization and ICT. Acceleration of the using processes of new developments in information and communication technologies in the manufacturing and services sectors. Scope of these technologies: for manufacturing parts of any complexity based on digital models, for example, by laser cutting or three-dimensional printers; design automation; "Embedded" computer systems for cars and others.
- Biotechnology. Development of biotechnologies, including in certain areas: biomedical technologies, biopharmaceuticals, food biotechnology, biomedicine, industrial biotechnology and bioenergy.
- Nanotechnologies. Development of methods for creating technologies and devices based on nanotechnology, which are primarily associated with a variety of possible areas of application. For example, the production and the conservation of energy, for example, new fuel elements, inexpensive photovoltaic solar cells etc. ; new materials with predetermined properties, which can be used in virtually all types of economic activities, from cosmetic products to the automotive industry.
- Medicine and Pharmacology. Development and implementation of high-tech production of new drugs based on natural (plants, animals, microorganisms, etc.) and synthetic raw materials.

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▪ Chemical Technologies. Synthesis of polymeric and composite materials with special functional properties, the development of new technologies and means of disposal of radioactive wastes and industrial wastes; chemical aspects of energy, such as the creation of new chemical current sources, the development of technologies for production of fuels from non-oil and renewable raw materials, high-energy substances and materials.

Thus, based on the priorities of economic development, science and technology for the period up to 2030 can be identified strategic priority of innovative technological development aimed at creating a breakthrough in high-tech industries, which will be based on the underlying technologies of 5 technological order and thereby create the conditions and prerequisites to move to the 6 technological order.

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